

Sustainable and healthy food consumption in Europe: an analysis of consumer purchase patterns, motivations and barriers towards foods from SFSCs

Journal:	<i>British Food Journal</i>
Manuscript ID	BFJ-01-2023-0058.R1
Manuscript Type:	Research Paper
Keywords:	Short Food Supply Chains, Consumers, Healthy diets, Good Practices, Motivation, barrier

SCHOLARONE™
Manuscripts

Sustainable and healthy food consumption in Europe: an analysis of consumer purchase patterns, motivations and barriers towards foods from SFSCs

Abstract

Purpose: The aim of this paper is to better understand European consumers' behaviour in relation to Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs), so as to provide insights to support their development as part of a sustainable food system. Specifically, it aims to analyse consumer purchase patterns, motivations and perceived barriers, and to identify patterns of behaviour amongst different consumer groups.

Design/methodology/approach: An online consumer survey was conducted in 12 European countries (n=2,419). Quantitative data analysis, including Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and cluster analysis, was undertaken using SPSS.

Findings: Four consumer clusters are named according to their behavioural stage in terms of SFSC engagement; Unaware Unengaged, Aware Unengaged, Motivationally Engaged, and Executively Engaged. Unaware Unengaged and Aware Unengaged are in the non-engagement phase of behaviour. Motivationally Engaged are motivationally activated to engage in the behaviour but fail to do so consistently. Executively Engaged is the fully engaged cluster, being motivated to act and purchasing local food on a frequent basis. The results show an interesting interplay between motivations and barriers, i.e. higher scores for motivations and lower scores for barriers do not necessarily translate into higher purchase frequency.

Originality: The research gleans insights into the contextual factors that may inhibit SFSC purchases in different consumer segments. It offers practical implications for policymakers and others seeking to develop SFSCs as part of a sustainable food system.

Keywords: *Short Food Supply Chains, consumers, motivations, barriers, Europe, Good Practices, healthy diets*

Paper Type: Research paper

1. Introduction

The global food system has undergone significant modernisation and structural change, which has consolidated power towards large scale actors such as processors and retailers (Carolan, 2021; Corvo *et al.*, 2021). Conversely, farmers face decreasing autonomy and a lower portion of the total added value of their produce (Horlings and Marsden, 2011). This concentration of power, along with improvements in long-distance transportation, technical advances and urbanisation, has created long and complicated supply chains, reducing the connection between primary producers and consumers. Such systems are considered to be ‘conventional’ as they represent the dominant production system in the developed world (Therond *et al.*, 2017).

Notwithstanding the many benefits of conventional supply chains in efficiently providing large volumes of food at low prices to large populations, the potentially adverse impacts of such chains are well documented. These include their link to increased price volatility, negative environmental impacts such as global warming, concerns about food safety and highly processed foods, and broader social aspects relating to the disappearance of the iconic “family farm” and negative impacts on rural/regional economic development (Kneafsey *et al.* 2013; Sacchi *et al.*, 2018; Wang *et al.*, 2021). Climate change, the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the COVID-19 pandemic have heightened concerns about the resilience of conventional supply chains (Michel-Villarreal *et al.*, 2021). The overall result is tensions within such chains, changes in consumers’ demands, with a growing influence of citizens in the nature of such chains. Indeed, such concerns point to the need for technical, social or institutional innovations, and alternative modes of food production, distribution and consumption to enable system change (Doernberg *et al.*, 2022).

Alternative food chains (e.g., farmers’ markets, on-farm direct sales, community supported agriculture) have consequently developed, with a positioning that is often in opposition to globalised commodity-based conventional chains (Goodman *et al.*, 2012). Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) are central to the alternative food movement discourse and have gained popularity throughout Europe (Augère-Granier, 2016 ; Giampietri *et al.*, 2016; Mundler and Laughrea, 2016) as a result of changes in consumer attitudes and preferences with respect to commoditisation (Ilbery and Maye, 2005), industrialisation (Watts *et al.*, 2017), and globalisation of food (Goodman *et al.*, 2012). SFSCs are also associated with a holistic view of sustainability, which encompasses the economy, society and the environment (Jarzębowski *et al.*, 2020).

However, SFSCs can be more than alternative systems; they can be viewed as a means by which to enhance sustainability of the food system overall. Such thinking aligns with a shift in attention “from ‘alternative’ food to ‘sustainable’ food” (Maxey, LonginEnthve2007). The IPCC argues that demand side interventions such as modifications to food choices and a reduction in food loss and food waste can reduce GHG emissions and enhance food system resilience. SFSCs can play a role here (Mbow *et al.*, 2019). For example, Chiffolleau and Dourian (2020) suggest that SFSCs could change attitudes and behaviours towards food, with the potential to ‘de-commodify food, both culturally and technologically, generate new quality standards beyond the scope of both industrial products and geographical indication labelling schemes, and procure diverse safe food that is accessible to all’. They also suggest that SFSCs have the potential to stimulate changes in the consumer behaviour towards healthier diets. SFSCs are thought to promote health in particular contexts because of the agricultural practices and food production and processing techniques used (Chiffolleau and Durrian, 2020). For example, some studies (e.g. Longin and Würschum, 2016; Meynard *et al.*, 2017) draw attention to the nutritional potential of ancient varieties and landraces - typically cultivated more frequently in SFSCs than conventional chains - for healthy and diversified diets. Other authors provide examples of SFSCs that are deliberately developed to enable consumers access food that has been produced with a limited number of synthetic inputs e.g. pesticides, hormones or synthetic additives (Michel-Villarreal *et al.*, 2021). Local food, especially fruits, vegetables, meat and dairy products, is generally perceived as fresh, and not highly processed and therefore is often presented as a healthy option (Enthoven and Broeck, 2021). Indirect impacts of SFSCs on sustainability within the food system relate to learning and participation, and creating awareness about sustainability-related issues in the food system (Doernberg *et al.* 2022).

83 Indeed, different types of SFSCs have been supported by urban food policies for these reasons
84 (Doernberg *et al.*, 2022).

85 On the supply side, it is observed that SFSCs can improve farm incomes, promote sustainable farming
86 systems and contribute to local, rural, economic development (Jarzębowski *et al.*, 2020). They provide
87 an opportunity to increase margins, (Trobe, 2001), stimulate diversification and entrepreneurship
88 (Morris and Buller, 2003) and develop new skills (Brown and Miller, 2008). From a socio-economic
89 perspective, SFSCs promote localisation of food in efforts to preserve livelihoods, traditional farmed
90 landscapes and rural heritage (Goodman *et al.*, 2012). A reconnection between consumers and
91 producers provides greater opportunities for differentiation and help consumers to consider attributes
92 that are central to a food system that is economically, socially and environmentally sustainable
93 (Marsden *et al.*, 2000).

94 Overall the potential economic, environmental, and social (including health and nutrition) benefits of
95 SFSCs present opportunities to address several of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the
96 United Nations, specifically SDG2 (zero hunger), SDG8 (decent work and economic growth), SDG11
97 (sustainable cities and communities), SDG12 (responsible consumption and production), SDG 13
98 (climate) and SDG 15 (life on land). The social impact of SFSCs corresponds with SDG2, while the
99 economic impact of SFSFCs correspond with SDGs 8, 11 and 12 and the environmental impact of
100 SFSCs correspond with SDGs 13 and 15 (Zimon *et al.*, 2020).

101 *Consumer perspectives on SFSCs*

102 Agreement on what constitutes a SFSC is lacking among academics and policymakers but a general
103 definition provided by EIP AGRI (2015) describes SFSCs as those that aim to create value by reducing
104 the number of steps in the food chain from producer to consumer. Within an EU context, a more nuanced
105 definition of a SFSC is defined within Regulation (EU) No. 1305/2013 (Article 2) as “a supply chain
106 involving a limited number of economic operators, committed to cooperation, local economic
107 development, and close geographical and social relations between producers, processors and
108 consumers” (European Commission, 2013). For the purpose of this paper (undertaken in the context of
109 the EU-funded agroBRIDGES¹ project), a SFSC is defined as follows: ‘*Short food supply chains have
110 as few links as possible between the food producer and the consumer/citizen who eats the food*’
111 (agroBRIDGES, 2021).

112 While SFSCs can provide many benefits from an economic, environmental and social perspective, they
113 account for a limited proportion of retail sales globally and do not fully address consumer needs in all
114 contexts. The barriers associated with SFSCs are many and varied as they vary substantially in their
115 approaches, motivations, actors and operation (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2021). SFSCs depend on actors mobilising
116 resources of various kinds: skills, knowledge, labour, capital, buildings, etc. They also depend on
117 external factors such as enabling policies, finance and regulation. These may not always be supportive
118 of SFSCs.

119 Despite the extensive literature on SFSCs, an understanding of the barriers that hinder their use by
120 consumers remain fragmented (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019). This is partially due to the wide variation in types
121 of SFSCs. Some follow traditional formats (e.g., farm sales, farmers’ markets, urban agriculture),
122 whereas others have developed contemporary approaches (e.g., community supported agriculture
123 (CSA), vegetable box schemes, online sales, food hubs, etc.) (Kneafsey *et al.*, 2013; EIP-AGRI, 2015;
124 Ribeiro *et al.*, 2019). Another limitation is that the literature often takes a producer perspective (Ribeiro
125 *et al.*, 2019) and the challenges of producers and consumers are often conflated rather than disentangled
126 (e.g. Carroll and Fahy, 2015; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2021). Despite these shortcomings, it is possible to identify
127 specific factors (contextual, psychological, etc.) that influence consumers’ decision-making with respect
128 to SFSCs (see Table 1).

¹ AgroBRIDGES, aims to build bridges between producers and consumers as well as rebalance farmers’ market position.

129 **Table I**

130 Consumers' motivations for choosing SFSC products are multiple. In line with behavioural theories,
 131 attitudes towards local food as well as other psychological factors such as beliefs, values, perceived
 132 behavioural control, perceived consumer effectiveness and social norms have been identified as
 133 antecedents to motivation (intention) to purchase food through SFSCs (Vermeir and Verbeke, 2008;
 134 Nurse *et al.*, 2012; Shin and Hancer, 2016). In their review of factors influencing local food
 135 consumption, Feldmann and Hamm (2015) highlight the importance of increasing consumer
 136 information and knowledge to develop positive attitudes towards local products. However, while
 137 consumer's motivations to buy products may be high, a low real or perceived availability of the good
 138 may hamper that motivation (Vermeir and Verbeke, 2006). Thus, the purpose of this paper is to obtain
 139 obtaining further consumer insights on the extent to which such motivations and barriers influence
 140 European consumer behaviour with regards to SFSCs, so as to support the development of actions to
 141 enhance SFSCs.

142

143 **2. Theoretical approach**

144 A common criticism of established theories such as the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) in
 145 explaining different consumer behaviours is the under-investigation of contextual variables denoted in
 146 Table 1 (Peattie, 2010). An established research finding is that the motivations (i.e. intentions) of
 147 individuals only loosely translate into actions; this is known as the attitude-behaviour gap or intention
 148 behaviour-gap (Nguyen *et al.*, 2019). Critically, not all behaviours are affected by such a gap as the
 149 higher the perceived costs of an action, the lesser the effect motivations have on actual behaviours
 150 (Farjam *et al.*, 2019). It is posited that behaviour is enacted when the related behavioural costs are low.
 151 However, attitudes and motivations become inconsequential when individuals have to bear significant
 152 costs (Viera *et al.*, 2023). The cost of an action usually depends on the efforts necessary to execute it;
 153 for example, the inconvenience of purchasing SFSC products. This low-cost hypothesis suggests that
 154 the lower the personal costs in a situation, the easier it is for individuals to conduct a behaviour. The
 155 literature has consequently increasingly pointed towards the importance of assessing barriers and their
 156 role in moderating the relationship between intention and behaviour (Nguyen *et al.*, 2019).

157 Numerous psychological theories support a dichotomous classification of reasons to pursue a particular
 158 behaviour (i.e. reasons for and reasons against), which can be used to explain behavioural-gaps (Sahu
 159 *et al.*, 2020). Such theories and related concepts include attitude-behaviour-context theory (Guagnano
 160 *et al.*, 1995), functional theorising (Snyder 1992), psychological coherence (Nowak *et al.*, 2000), the
 161 health-belief model (Janz and Becker, 1984), sense-making (Thomas *et al.*, 1993) and cost-benefit
 162 models (Thaler, 1999). These theories present dichotomous, contrasting motivational forces in the form
 163 of facilitators and inhibitors (Sahu *et al.*, 2020). For instance, Dual Factor Theory posits that two distinct
 164 factors, facilitators and inhibitors, influence decision-making (Tandon *et al.*, 2021). However, while
 165 both encouraging and hindering factors predict behaviour adoption, motivations and barriers are not
 166 merely opposites of one another. For example, the presence of barriers predict behavioural rejection,
 167 however their absence does not necessarily favour adoption of a behaviour (Rey-Moreno and Medina-
 168 Molina, 2020; Tandon *et al.*, 2021). Motivations and barriers hence offer two distinct perspectives that
 169 shape consumer behaviour. Moreover, the assessment of reasons for and against a behaviour is context-
 170 dependent; thereby providing rich contextual information (Sahu *et al.*, 2020).

171 Individuals are more likely to initiate behaviour when their psychological resources are plentiful and
 172 when opportunity costs (effort needed to enact behaviour) are low (i.e., favourable contexts)
 173 (Kwasnicka *et al.*, 2016). The barriers to SFSC consumption can be depicted as contextual factors
 174 relating to local food purchase (Feldmann and Hamm, 2015). Context serves as a mediator between
 175 attitude and behaviour of consumers; it can also reinforce attitude and behaviour (Sirieix *et al.*, 2013).
 176 When the context remains impartial or supportive (e.g. local food is easy to identify and available),
 177 attitude tend to align more closely with behaviour. Conversely, attitude outperforms context if attitude
 178 is particularly strong (e.g. if consumers are very committed to local food, higher prices will not impede

179 purchasing behaviour) (Feldmann and Hamm, 2015). Contextual factors outperform attitudes when they
180 are strongly negative or extremely positive (Guagnano *et al.*, 1995). Interestingly, Stern (2000) found
181 that contextual factors may have a stronger influence on behaviour than attitude. Some of the contextual
182 barriers most commonly denoted in SFSC research are availability, convenience, price, seasonal variety,
183 etc. (Table 1).

184 Behaviour can also reinforce habits, e.g. local food purchases might create the habit of regularly visiting
185 farmers' markets (Feldmann and Hamm, 2015). Heterogeneity in the motivation–behaviour relation and
186 the modest effects of attitude change on behaviour change have reignited enthusiasm in investigating
187 habits and their role in affecting behaviour (Verplanken and Orbell, 2022). The concept of 'habit'
188 implies something that a consumer does regularly, but does not necessarily correspond to all food
189 purchase situations. Therefore, habits do not always mediate between context and behaviour. Indeed,
190 the adoption of new products is not always dependent on motivation but instead emerges from
191 consumer's habitual repetition of past behaviour. Habit slips, hence, may occur with little input from
192 product related motivations (Labrecque *et al.*, 2017). Even when other resources are limited, behavioural
193 maintenance can occur if the behaviour is habitually instigated. As motivation decreases and barriers
194 increase, the need for self-regulatory effort is increased in order to ensure a behaviour continues despite
195 less than optimal conditions (Kwasnicka *et al.*, 2016). This self-regulation is dependent on individuals'
196 motivations, barriers, and habits.

197 Much academic interest has focused on understanding the various drivers and obstacles influencing the
198 consumption of local food. However, the scope of these studies is often confined to relatively narrow
199 geographical ranges (e.g. Brown *et al.*, 2009; Fleury *et al.*, 2016; González-Azcárate *et al.*, 2021;
200 Kovács *et al.*, 2022; Mesić *et al.*, 2020). This limitation is especially important as the distribution of
201 short supply chains is not restricted to the local, i.e. it is not defined by spatial proximity. Instead, SFSCs
202 can be widely distributed based on a small number of intermediaries between the producer and
203 consumer, i.e. spatially extended SFSCs (Marsden *et al.*, 2000). It is therefore important to consider
204 consumer profiles that are not country specific but encapsulate consumers from a pan-European
205 perspective.

206 To increase consumption of SFSC products it is necessary to consider behavioural change interventions.
207 However, consideration of consumers' position on the behavioural change journey is required. Both
208 Leeuwis *et al.* (2022) and Michaelsen and Esch (2021) propose a framework that defines three stages
209 of behaviour change that could be useful for such purposes:

- 210 (1) non-engagement, where the consumer is either unaware or aware of the benefits of a behaviour but
211 does not intend to take action,
- 212 (2) motivational engagement, where the consumer contemplates the action and
- 213 (3) executive engagement where the action is initiated, continued and maintained until it becomes a
214 habit.

215
216 This research follows Feldmann and Hamm's (2015) recommendation for studies concerning
217 consumers and SFSCs. In their review of consumers' preferences for local food they suggest cross-
218 country research is much needed where several product categories are considered. Therefore, the
219 contributions of this study are manifold. Firstly, most studies that focus on SFSC motivations and
220 barriers do so without considering behaviour across multiple product categories. This research aims to
221 segment consumers across 12 European countries based on their motivations, barriers, and purchase
222 frequency of a range of SFSC products. The research will glean insights into the contextual factors that
223 may, or may not, inhibit SFSC purchases in different consumer segments. The study also aims to
224 decipher if consumer segments are categorised by their respective stages of behavioural change. This
225 may help explain the attitude/intention-behaviour gap that is often under investigated using theories
226 such as the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Hassan *et al.*, 2016).

227

3. Methods

Informed by the literature, and insights from semi-structured interviews with producers, consumers/customers/retailers and intermediaries across 12 European countries (not reported here, see Hyland *et al.*, 2021), a questionnaire was developed to investigate consumers' perspectives on food from SFSCs. The questionnaire first captured information on socio-demographic factors including type of community, age, gender, level of education, household income and job category. The purchase frequency of a range of products consumers may purchase through SFSCs was captured by asking participants to choose between "weekly", "fortnightly", "monthly", "a few times a year" or "never" for the following food groups: "fruit, vegetables, herbs", "meat", "baked good (e.g. bread)", "fish", "dairy", "eggs", "ready meals", "non-perishable foods e.g. preserves, condiments etc.", "other, including juices". The motivations and barriers for purchasing products through SFSCs was then captured on a 7-point sliding scale ranging from "Extremely important" to "Not important at all". Lastly, the values of participants in terms of their food choices was captured by asking participants to state their level of agreement with statements using a 7-point sliding scale ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree".

The questionnaire was administered to consumers in 12 geographically dispersed and diverse European countries, in the summer of 2021, to provide national and international consumer insights regarding SFSCs. To ensure meaningful data was gathered efficiently and effectively, a single research agency that maintained a panel of consumers for market research purposes was utilised to obtain consumer responses to the online survey from each country. The agency was selected to standardise procedures across countries as much as possible and ethical approval was obtained from Munster Technological University (MTU). Consumers were required to indicate informed consent in advance of completing the survey and agroBRIDGES project partners translated the survey into local languages.

The research agency tested the survey with a small number of respondents and following minor modifications, the survey was conducted in all 12 European countries with 2,419 consumers participating in the survey. Data from the online survey was captured using M3 Panel and Dynata - the specific platform used depended on the country. At the conclusion of the survey exercise, the research agency commissioned to distribute the survey compiled the data and forwarded it to TEAGASC for statistical analysis.

Statistical analyses

Statistical analyses were carried out using SPSS 29 (SPSS 29, Chicago, IL, USA). Survey results were analysed statistically in a variety of ways including Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and cluster analysis.

Principal Component Analysis

PCA identifies common factors to account for most of the variation in the data and is performed by examining the pattern of correlations among independent variables (i.e. questionnaire statements). It in effect reduces the dimensionality of the data. When these variables are highly correlated, they are effectively 'saying the same thing' and are described as components (Field, 2009). The subsequently acquired factor loadings are merely the correlations among all individuals' answers to each of the questionnaire statements with the derived component score. The components extracted from the PCA are subsequently used as classification criteria to cluster respondents into types (Aprine *et al.*, 2016; Kumar and Smith, 2018). These groupings are internally homogenous, while being externally heterogeneous from one another (Janssens *et al.* 2008). The content of a component was best interpreted by examining items with factor loadings of 0.4 or above; such factors are considered to be 'fair' (Costello and Osborne 2011). Cronbach's alpha was applied to test the reliability and internal consistency of the derived factor loadings (Pallant, 2010).

276 *Cluster Analysis*

277 To categorise individuals, cluster analysis was used to segment consumers based on PCA component
278 scores. The determination of the optimal number of clusters was achieved through hierarchical cluster
279 analysis (Burns and Burns, 2008). The selection of the appropriate number of clusters was judged by
280 taking into consideration clusters which were clearly distinct and meaningful, while also maintaining a
281 reasonable sample size (Devlin *et al.*, 2012). The superior K-means methodology identified aggregates
282 of individuals in multidimensional space (Janssens *et al.*, 2008; Reedy *et al.*, 2010). Within a specific
283 cluster consumers are as similar as possible to all the other individuals in the same cluster, whereas a
284 consumer is as distinct as possible from others in different clusters (Reedy *et al.*, 2010). A Varimax
285 rotation was implemented to increase the interpretability of the results (Field, 2009). A statement was
286 only retained if the loading factor was at least 0.35 (Janssens *et al.* 2008).

287 Normality was determined from the central limit theorem. Chi-square analysis determined significant
288 associations between categorical variables (ordinal and nominal data). A significant result between
289 categorical variables was examined by converting the adjusted residuals (Z-scores) to Chi-square values
290 and testing those against a Chi-square distribution (Bonferroni corrected p-value) (MacDonald and
291 Gardner, 2000; Sharpe, 2019).

292 In order to investigate whether geographic location exerted a significant influence on cluster
293 membership, the 12 countries were categorised into four distinct regions. Eastern Europe comprised
294 consumers from Latvia, Lithuania, and Poland. The Mediterranean grouping consisted of Greece, Italy,
295 Spain, and Turkey. The Nordic classification included Denmark and Finland, while Western Europe
296 comprised France, Ireland, and the Netherlands.

297

4. Results

Sample Profile

A total sample size of 2,419 respondents was gathered from 12 countries in Europe with each country contributing between 8.3 - 8.7% (i.e. approximately 200 – 211 respondents per country) of the total sample size. The countries include Denmark, Finland, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Poland, Spain and Turkey. An analysis of the sample used in this study reveals that broadly, the sample profile is equally distributed among males and females (males = 49.7%; females = 51.1%). In addition, all the respondents surveyed were aged over 18 years, with the median age falling within the 40 – 54 age range, while most lived in urban or densely populated areas (51.2%), followed by those living in suburban areas (31.1%).

PCA and Cluster Analysis

The questionnaire items were subjected to PCA. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy was found to be greater than 0.6 (0.952), thereby verifying that the dataset was appropriate for PCA. Subsequently, the Bartlett's test of sphericity was seen to be significant ($p < 0.01$), thus indicating that PCA could proceed. Interpretation of the scree plot revealed inflexions that justified retaining three components. PCA revealed the presence of three components that explained 31.12%, 15.07%, and 10.30% of the variance. The components are named: motivations, barriers, and purchase frequency. Cronbach alpha's > 0.5 are considered acceptable as evidence of a common factor underlying the responses (Nunnally 1967). The Cronbach alpha for each component was 0.931, 0.924, and 0.916 respectively, thereby, signifying a high level of reliability for each. The PCA loadings after Varimax rotation are presented in Table 2.

319 Table II

320 The components derived from PCA are used to segment consumers. The largest cluster represents
321 31.4%, followed by groupings that comprise of 27.8%, 22.0%, and 18.8% of respondents. Table 3
322 presents the final cluster centres which are computed as the mean for each variable within each final
323 cluster and reflect the characteristics of the typical consumer for each cluster. The naming convention
324 of the clusters broadly follows the frameworks of Leeuwis *et al.* (2022) and Michaelsen and Esch (2021)
325 who propose varying levels of consumer engagement where executive engagement represents habitual
326 and frequent purchasing behaviour. The clusters were consequently labelled the Unaware Unengaged
327 (22.0%), the Aware Unengaged (27.8%), the Motivationally Engaged (18.8%), and the Executively
328 Engaged (31.4%).

329 The Unaware Unengaged and Aware Unengaged clusters are both situated within the non-engagement
330 phase of behavioural change. The Motivated Engaged cluster has progressed further in the behavioural
331 change process but has not yet acquired the habitual behaviour observed in the Executively Engaged
332 cluster. Detailed descriptions of each segment are provided in the following sections.

333 Table III

334

335 *The Unaware Unengaged (22.0%)*

336 This cohort of consumers exhibits the lowest level of motivation when it comes to acquiring SFSC
337 products. Nonetheless, their frequency of purchasing local food items ranks as the second highest. The
338 presence of a low barrier score facilitates their propensity for frequent purchases (Table 3). In terms of
339 demographic composition, this segment displays a significantly greater likelihood of being composed
340 of consumers from Eastern Europe in contrast to all other groupings (Table 4). When examining many
341 of the categories related to the monthly expenditure on SFSCs, this cluster does not demonstrate
342 statistically significant distinctions in comparison to the Motivationally Engaged (Table 5). However,
343 it is worth noting that this cluster is significantly more inclined to allocate 0% of their monthly food
344 expenditure to SFSCs and less inclined to allocate 51-75%, as opposed to the Motivationally Engaged
345 group (Table 5).

346 Table IV

347

348 *The Aware Unengaged (27.8%)*

349 This cluster is characterised by a higher level of motivation compared to the Unaware Unengaged group.
 350 However, it struggles to manifest this motivation in terms of actual purchasing actions. Despite being
 351 more engaged in the concept of SFSCs, it encounters greater obstacles than the Unaware Unengaged
 352 (Table 3). This could elucidate why it falls short in acquiring SFSC products. In fact, it exhibits the least
 353 frequent purchasing behaviour among all the clusters (Table 3). It does not possess any unique
 354 demographical characteristics evident in other clusters (Table 4). The value of monthly SFSC purchases
 355 as a proportion of total grocery shopping expenditure is significantly lower across all ranges compared
 356 to all other segments (Table 5). The exception being the 76-100% value range where the Aware
 357 Unengaged is not significantly different to those in the Unaware Unengaged cluster (Table 5).

358

359 Table V

360 *The Motivationally Engaged (18.8%)*

361 The cluster known as the Motivationally Engaged achieved the highest scores when it comes to their
 362 motivations regarding SFSCs. Despite their strong motivation, their actual purchases of SFSC products
 363 did not surpass those of the Unaware Unengaged segment. Furthermore, this cluster obtained lower
 364 scores in terms of barriers when compared to all other groups (Table 3). Hence, a noticeable disparity
 365 exists between their professed intentions and their actions, especially considering the relatively low
 366 contextual barriers. Members belonging to the Motivationally Engaged cluster are significantly more
 367 likely to originate from Western Europe when compared to the other groups (Table 4). Additionally, in
 368 comparison to all other segments, a significantly higher proportion of individuals in this cluster come
 369 from rural areas, fall within the age range of 55-64, and are retired (Table 4). Notably, significantly less
 370 Motivationally Engaged consumers have an annual household income below €25,000 (Table 4).

371

372

373 *The Executively Engaged (31.4%)*

374 Individuals within the Executively Engaged cluster achieved the highest purchase frequency and ranked
 375 second in terms of their motivation levels. Members of this group perceive barriers related to SFSCs to
 376 a greater extent than those in the other clusters. However, they manage to maintain their SFSC product
 377 purchasing frequency irrespective of the high barrier encountered (Table 3). In terms of demographics,
 378 this cluster is significantly more likely to include individuals from Mediterranean regions and
 379 significantly less likely to comprise Nordic consumers (Table 4). A significantly higher proportion of
 380 cluster members reside in urban areas (Table 4). Furthermore, in comparison to other segments, the
 381 occurrence of a single individual conducting all household shopping is significantly lower within this
 382 cluster (Table 5). When it comes to the value of monthly SFSC purchases, the Executively Engaged
 383 exhibits significantly higher expenditures across all ranges in comparison to those who fall into the
 384 Unaware Unengaged and Aware Unengaged categories (Table 5). Although they share similarities with
 385 the Executively Engaged group, they also significantly diverge in many aspects related to the
 386 proportions of their monthly SFSC purchases (Table 5).

387

5. Discussion

Starting from the premise that SFSCs can have a role in enabling transitions towards more sustainable production and consumption practices, including having a potential role in shaping new foodscapes or food environments (Chiffolleau and Dourian, 2020), this research gives insights into how greater consumer participation in SFSCs could be enabled through tapping into motivations and addressing actual/perceived barriers. The results in this study show that top motivations driving consumers' purchase of foods through SFSCs include product quality (in terms of taste, freshness and healthiness), food safety concerns as well as support of local farmers, food producers and the local economy. Notwithstanding these motivations, and the high level of purchase of a range of products, consumers in this study also identify a range of barriers that need addressing. They report that accessibility, expense, variety, trust, and the ability to identify products are the most arduous barriers associated with SFSCs. This finding corroborates the top-identified barriers in literature associated with consumer purchase of SFSC foods.

The consumer decision-making process is complex, and the significance of motives and obstacles may fluctuate across different product categories (Padel and Foster, 2005). This study counteracts this by assessing consumers SFSC motivations and barriers as well as their habitual purchasing behaviour across multiple product categories. PCA and cluster analysis yielded four clusters of consumers. The groupings are named according to their respective behavioural stage in terms of SFSC engagement; the Unaware Unengaged, the Aware Unengaged, the Motivationally Engaged, and the Executively Engaged. The engagement phases are characterised by the level or type of involvement in a behaviour. The Unaware Unengaged and the Aware Unengaged are both in the non-engagement phase of behaviour. Conversely, the Motivationally Engaged are motivationally activated to engage in the behaviour but fail to do so consistently. The Executively Engaged are the only cluster truly engaged in SFSCs as they are motivated to act but also purchase local food on a frequent basis. The results of the cluster analysis show an interesting interplay between motivations and barriers, i.e. higher scores for motivations and lower scores for barriers do not necessarily translate into higher purchase frequency.

Much like the findings from Birch *et al.* (2018) there was no clear relationship between an increased frequency of local food purchases and motivational factors. The Motivationally Engaged displayed the highest motivation score but scored lower in purchase frequency than even the Unaware Unengaged. Young *et al.* (2010) describes this a behavioural gap; in their study they state that 30% of consumers report motivation to act in a particular manner but struggle to translate this into purchases. Those with stronger habits typically repeated their past behaviour (Labrecque *et al.*, 2017). This may explain why the Executively Engaged has the highest purchase frequency despite scoring highest in terms of barriers. Their purchase of SFSCs has become so habitual and automatic that barriers are not as burdensome as for other clusters. Indeed, it is their strong psychological resources and habits that act as supporting mechanisms that foster behaviour maintenance (Kwasnicka *et al.*, 2016). Reflecting on the size of the clusters and the relative impact of motivations and barriers as presented in Table 3, the results suggest a greater focus on addressing barriers might be more fruitful than addressing motivations. This is most evident in the Unaware Unengaged cluster who despite scoring lowest in terms of motivation reported the second highest purchase frequency. Hence, despite being unengaged in the concept of SFSCs when faced with little barriers they frequently purchased local food.

Individual and collective initiatives can be set up to target the drawbacks of SFSCs, to boost their accessibility, affordability and transparency, and facilitate contact points between consumers and producers in order to increase the market share of SFSCs (González-Azcárate *et al.*, 2021). For example, producers' cooperation in establishing food hubs could potentially overcome many of the aforementioned issues highlighted by consumers (Berti and Mulligan, 2016). Cleveland *et al.* (2014) contend that food hubs provide many of the benefits of traditional SFSCs (such as harnessing greater profits for primary producers) as well as the advantages associated with conventional supply chains (such as cost efficiencies and offering greater choice to consumers). These collaborative ventures could therefore help consumers access SFSC products more easily while offering a more varied product range

1
2
3 441 than that available from an individual producer (Hyland and Macken-Walsh, 2022). The cost efficiency
4 442 of the hubs may also enable local products to be priced more competitively. EU member states could
5 443 target EU Rural Development funding (under the CAP Pillar 2) and Structural Funds (under Cohesion
6 444 Policy) towards SFSCs and in particular, collaborative food hubs for the benefit of both producers and
7 445 consumers. A growing recognition of the influence of the physical (“built”) environment, including the
8 446 retail food environment, in determining food choice (Frank *et al.*, 2022), could provide an argument
9 447 for the support of such initiatives from a nutrition and health perspective.
10 448

11 449 Using exemplar Good Practices from across Europe - defined as a description of a case where learnings
12 450 are identified, which can be useful, adaptable and applicable for others – plausible solutions to the
13 451 consumer-identified barriers are proposed². The Good Practices are existing initiatives within the
14 452 countries where the consumer survey took place, alongside some international representations across
15 453 Europe. Two examples of food hub Good Practices illustrate how collaborative structures enable access
16 454 to SFSC products via the use of digital technologies. *Rechtstreek* for instance, provides an online
17 455 platform where consumers can order local agri-food products in the Netherlands. Once the orders are
18 456 collected, suppliers who are farmers and producers within 50 km of *Rechtstreek*'s collection points in
19 457 Rotterdam or The Hague receive the orders and deliver the products to *Rechtstreek*'s distribution centres.
20 458 From there, the products go to regional pick-up points where consumers can collect their orders. *Pora*
21 459 *na Pola* is another example of an online marketplace that delivers fresh, local and high quality products
22 460 from over 80 craft food manufacturers to consumers all over Poland. It offers a subscription based
23 461 service, which focuses on the consumer's identified preferences. Depending on the subscription plan,
24 462 there are discounts and free delivery services, which can further help to address the issues of
25 463 affordability and access. Mobile farmers' markets can also help mitigate the problem of consumer
26 464 access to SFSC products. The Good Practice *Mobilius Turgelis* for example is a mobile farmers' market
27 465 that operates in various cities in Lithuania. It serves different city districts on different days of the week,
28 466 specifically from Tuesdays to Saturdays. These markets are primarily located near supermarkets or
29 467 public administration buildings and are present in the biggest cities. Consumers access the products
30 468 directly - mostly from food trucks, and the agricultural cooperative, “Lietuviško ūkio kokybė”,
31 469 coordinates the mobile farmers' market.
32 470

33 471 With respect to affordability specifically, a plausible solution is to reduce the financial outlay on local
34 472 foods through substituting labour for payment. An example is the self-picking berry model in Finland
35 473 where lots of berry farmers, especially strawberry, raspberry and blackcurrant farmers, allow self-
36 474 picking of the berries on their farms. In practice, consumers often visit the berry farm with their own
37 475 dishes, enhancing environmental sustainability and reducing costs. The dishes are weighed prior to
38 476 picking, after which consumers can pick as many berries as they wish. After picking, the dish is re-
39 477 weighed and the consumer pays the farmer for the berries picked. The removal of the cost of labour,
40 478 and packaging in many cases, enables the farmer to sell at a lower price. The issue of affordability can
41 479 also be addressed through a stronger focus on value rather than price per se. Marsden *et al.* (2000) note
42 480 that conventional supply chains have created a disconnect between producers and consumers, which
43 481 can lead to consumers overlooking some of the positive attributes of a food system that is economically,
44 482 socially and environmentally sustainable. The Irish not-for-profit organization Airfield Estate is an
45 483 example of a Good Practice that addresses the consumer-specific barriers of lack of awareness of the
46 484 benefits of SFSCs and unavailability of products throughout the year. Airfield Estate runs ‘hands-on’
47 485 education and awareness raising activities in order to ensure consumers understand the impact their
48 486 food choices have on them as individuals, their families, the society and the planet.
49 487

50 488 While these good practices can help to address the barriers, and such actions are likely to be appreciated
51 489 by consumers in the Aware Unengaged and the Executively Engaged in particular, it is clear that
52 490 addressing the barriers alone will not result in higher levels of purchase for consumers such as those in
53 491 the Motivationally Engaged. Indeed, the Motivationally Engaged highlights the challenges in effecting
54 492 behavioural change; motivations to purchase foods through SFSCs are high, and perceived barriers are
55 493 relatively low, however this does not translate into purchase. As such, it is clear that there is a

56
57
58
59
60 ² <https://www.agrobridges.eu/interactive-catalogue-agrobridges>

1
2
3 494 motivation-behaviour gap. This is not a new phenomenon in relation to sustainable consumption. Indeed
4 495 the term “green gap” has been coined to refer to the discrepancy between consumers self-stated growing
5 496 concern for the environment and what they actually do to support the environment (ElHaffar *et al.* 2020).
6 497 Various reasons can be proposed for such a gap, many of which reflect criticisms of the theory of
7 498 planned behaviour such as not taking account of individual, social and institutional factors. Indeed as
8 499 noted by ElHaffar *et al.* 2020, the rational, utility-maximising economic paradigm can be limited in
9 500 such contexts with behaviour being more highly influenced by emotions and cognitive biases. Factors
10 501 such as competing values (e.g. concern for the environment vs pleasure seeking/hedonic values),
11 502 counter-incentives (e.g. time saving as a result of not purchasing through SFSCs) and a lack of relevant
12 503 options can result in a value-action gap. Indeed, for many consumers the altruistic values that favour
13 504 the purchase of more sustainable products cannot replace hedonic and egoistic values associated with
14 505 purchasing certain types of products (ElHaffar *et al.*, 2020). Both types of values are at play and need
15 506 to be considered. Inertia and consumption habits can also be factors (Wiederhold and Martinez, 2018),
16 507 with benefit certainty indirectly mediating intentions (ElHaffar *et al.* 2020). Moreover, where there is
17 508 uncertainty regarding collective social gains, maximising self-interest can outweigh the cost of
18 509 undertaking more sustainable behaviours (Johnstone and Tan, 2015). Van de Grint *et al.* (2021) also
19 510 highlights the possibility of co-existence of different motives within the same person, reporting that
20 511 self-interest and altruistic concerns are not mutually exclusive in how people see themselves or in how
21 512 others see them. Strategies undertaken by consumers to address a lack of consistency between
22 513 motivations and intentions, and which indirectly promote the gap between intention and behaviour, are
23 514 termed neutralisation techniques (ElHaffar *et al.* 2020). They include denial of responsibility, denial of
24 515 injury (Atkinson and Kim, 2015; Johnstone and Tan, 2015), appeal to higher loyalties (Johnstone and
25 516 Tan, 2015), and condemning the condemner (Gruber and Schlegelmilch, 2014).

26 517
27 518 Increased media attention on environmental and social issues has made consumers more conscious of
28 519 their behaviour and it has encouraged consumers to indicate their values through the purchase, or
29 520 intended purchase of certain goods. In the context of research related to SFSCs, impression
30 521 management or image motivations have been reported to be an important driver of organic consumption
31 522 by van de Grint *et al.* (2021). Furthermore, research by Richetin and Perugini (2022) found that
32 523 individuals make inferences about organic food consumers regarding basic personality traits, with
33 524 regular consumers of organic foods perceived to be more honest, more agreeable and more
34 525 conscientious and more open. Such consumption however does not always have positive reputational
35 526 consequences. Richetin and Perugini (2022) also found that organic consumers were judged as more
36 527 narcissistic and van de Grint *et al.* (2021) found that organic consumption might have reputational costs
37 528 as well as benefits. This might lead consumers who are motivated to purchase SFSC foods to be more
38 529 cautious in their purchasing practices. Indeed, Johnstone and Tan (2015) found that in addition to the
39 530 perceived difficulty of being green (note low level of perceived barriers in the Motivationally Engaged),
40 531 green stigma (meaning consumers’ negative or unfavourable perceptions of ‘green’ consumers and
41 532 ‘green’ messages) and green reservations (consumers’ uncertainty or ambivalence towards green
42 533 consumption practices, i.e. that participating in green consumption practices will not make a difference
43 534 to the environment), can influence green behaviour. Considering the low level of perceived barriers in
44 535 the Motivationally Engaged, it is likely that perceived difficulty is not a significant factor for those in
45 536 the cluster. Moreover, it is evident that Perceived Behaviour Control is not an issue for the
46 537 Motivationally Engaged. Green stigma however cannot be ruled out.

47 538
48 539 Reminding people of their values, making people care more about their values, encouraging and helping
49 540 people to take action, making it easier to act in a way that’s consistent with relevant values and making
50 541 it harder to act in a way that is inconsistent with relevant values are common recommendations to
51 542 address the intention-behaviour gap. Li *et al.* (2016) found that information channels that promote green
52 543 values can be effective in promoting the purchase of green products. Given the importance of
53 544 congruency between the promoted behaviour and the target group identity as noted by ElHaffar *et al.*,
54 545 (2020) in the effectiveness of such an approach, it is likely that this would be very effective for
55 546 consumers in three of the four clusters profiled here (Unaware Unengaged may be different). Digital
56 547 tools have a role to play too. Zapico *et al.* (2016) for example found that consumers often under-
57 548 estimate the amount of organic food they purchase, and that they significantly increase the amount of

1
2
3 549 organic food purchased when provided with feedback (via a data visualisation tool based on shopping
4 550 receipts) that provides such evidence. Armed with knowledge about actual (habitual) behaviour, they
5 551 can use this knowledge to trigger a change to align their actual shopping with their self-perception, thus
6 552 addressing cognitive dissonance and helping them to live up to their values
7 553

8 554 **6. Limitations of the work and suggestions for future studies**

10 555 It is recognised that online surveys have limitations concerning the populations that can be accessed
11 556 and the amount of data that can be collected from individual respondents. In this instance, it is felt
12 557 that the benefits of being able to efficiently conduct a consumer survey across 12 European countries
13 558 outweighed such limitations. However, to ensure a nuanced understanding of consumer perspectives
14 559 relating to SFSCs within an individual country, administering the survey through face-to-face
15 560 interviews, possibly complemented by qualitative methods (e.g. focus groups) could be beneficial.
16 561 Profiling the consumer segments further, e.g. in terms of Food Related Lifestyles (FRL) could also
17 562 yield additional actionable insights (Nie and Zepeda, 2011; Witzling and Shaw, 2019). This study was
18 563 limited in terms of investigating situational factors, such as place of purchase, and the impact of such
19 564 factors on purchasing behaviour for different product categories, and amongst consumers in different
20 565 clusters. Further research could investigate for instance if less motivated consumers more likely to
21 566 purchase SFSCs in certain contexts rather than others, e.g. particular products in particular types of
22 567 SFSCs. Given the strong influence of barriers on consumer behaviour in relation to SFSCs, research
23 568 to (co-) design, implement and evaluate the impact of interventions that address barriers for different
24 569 types of consumers in real-world contexts is likely to be a fruitful avenue of future research. Finally,
25 570 SFSCs involve two key actors: consumers and producers. Hence it would be useful to undertake
26 571 additional research to understand the impact of barriers and motivations, and the interplay between
27 572 these, on producers' behaviour in relation to participation in SFSCs.
28 573

30 573
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

7. References

- 574
- 575 AGRI, E., (2015). EIP-AGRI Focus Group-Innovative Short Food Supply Chain management.
- 576 agroBRIDGES., 2021. D1.2 Report on European and regional analysis of producer and consumers
- 577 needs and barriers towards SFSCs implementation. Document developed in the Framework of the
- 578 European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N°
- 579 101000788.
- 580 Alae-Carew, C., Green, R., Stewart, C., Cook, B., Dangour, A. D. and Scheelbeek, P. F., (2022). The
- 581 role of plant-based alternative foods in sustainable and healthy food systems: Consumption trends in
- 582 the UK. *Science of the Total Environment*, 807, p.151041.
- 583 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.151041>
- 584 Aprile, M.C., Caputo, V., Nayga Jr R..M. (2016). Consumers' preferences and attitudes toward local
- 585 food products. *Journal of Food Marketing*, 22 (1), pp. 19-42.
- 586 Atkinson L., and Kim Y. 2015 I drink it anyway and I know I shouldn't: understanding green
- 587 consumers' positive evaluations of non-violating nongreen products and misleading green advertising.
- 588 *Environmental Communication* 9(1), pp. 37–57. DOI: 10.1080/17524032.2014.932817
- 589 Aubree, P., Brunori, G., Dvortsin, L., Galli, F., Gromasheva, O., Hoekstra, F., Karner, S., Lutz, J.,
- 590 Piccon, L. and Prior, A., (2013). Short Food Supply Chains as drivers of sustainable development.
- 591 Laboratorio di studi rurali Sismondi.
- 592 [http://www.foodlinkscommunity.net/fileadmin/documents_organicresearch/foodlinks/CoPs/evidence-](http://www.foodlinkscommunity.net/fileadmin/documents_organicresearch/foodlinks/CoPs/evidence-document-sfsc-cop.pdf)
- 593 [document-sfsc-cop.pdf](http://www.foodlinkscommunity.net/fileadmin/documents_organicresearch/foodlinks/CoPs/evidence-document-sfsc-cop.pdf)
- 594 Aubry, C. and Kebir, L., (2013). Shortening food supply chains: A means for maintaining agriculture
- 595 close to urban areas? The case of the French metropolitan area of Paris. *Food Policy*, 41, pp. 85-93.
- 596 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2013.04.006>
- 597 Augère-Granier, M. L., (2016). Short food supply chains and local food systems in the EU. EPRS:
- 598 European Parliamentary Research Service. Retrieved from
- 599 [https://policycommons.net/artifacts/1340881/short-food-supply-chains-and-local-food-systems-in-the-](https://policycommons.net/artifacts/1340881/short-food-supply-chains-and-local-food-systems-in-the-eu/1951844/)
- 600 [eu/1951844/](https://policycommons.net/artifacts/1340881/short-food-supply-chains-and-local-food-systems-in-the-eu/1951844/) on 14 Nov 2022. CID: 20.500.12592/c8n444.
- 601 Belletti, G. and Marescotti, A., (2020). Short food supply chains for promoting local food on local
- 602 markets. United Nations Industrial Development Organization
- 603 Berlina, A., Tepecik Diş, A. and Jungsberg, L., (2017). Local food systems formation: The potential
- 604 of local food initiatives in the Baltic Sea Region.
- 605 <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:norden.org:diva-4994>
- 606 Berti, G. and Mulligan, C., (2016). Competitiveness of small farms and innovative food supply
- 607 chains: The role of food hubs in creating sustainable regional and local food systems. *Sustainability*,
- 608 8(7), p.616. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8070616>
- 609 Bean, M. and Sharp, J.S., (2011). Profiling alternative food system supporters: The personal and
- 610 social basis of local and organic food support. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*, 26(3),
- 611 pp.243-254. DOI:10.1017/S1742170511000032
- 612 Bingen, J., Sage, J. and Sirieix, L., (2011). Consumer coping strategies: a study of consumers
- 613 committed to eating local. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 35(4), pp.410-419.
- 614 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1470-6431.2010.00949.x>
- 615 Birch, D. and Memery, J., (2020). Tourists, local food and the intention-behaviour gap. *Journal of*
- 616 *Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 43, pp.53-61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2020.02.006>

- 1
2
3 617 Birch, D., Memery, J. and Kanakarathne, M. D. S., (2018). The mindful consumer: Balancing egoistic
4 618 and altruistic motivations to purchase local food. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 40, pp.
5 619 221-228.
- 6
7 620 Brown E., Dury S. and Holdsworth M. (2009). Motivations of Consumers that use Local, Organic
8 621 Fruit and Vegetable Box Schemes in Central England and Southern France; *Appetite* 53, (2), pp. 183-
9 622 188. DOI: 10.1016/j.appet.2009.06.006
- 10
11 623 Brown, C., and S. Miller. (2008). The impacts of local markets: A review of research on farmers
12 624 markets and Community Supported Agriculture (CSA). *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*
13 625 90(5), pp. 1296 -1302.
- 14
15 626 Brown, C., (2003). Consumers' preferences for locally produced food: A study in southeast Missouri.
16 627 *American Journal of Alternative Agriculture*, 18(4), pp.213-224. DOI:
17 628 <https://doi.org/10.1079/AJAA200353>
- 18
19 629 Brumă, I. S., Vasiliu, C. D., Rodino, S., Butu, M., Tanasă, L., Doboş, S., Butu, A., Coca, O. and
20 630 Stefan, G., (2021). The Behavior of Dairy Consumers in Short Food Supply Chains during COVID-
21 631 19 Pandemic in Suceava Area, Romania. *Sustainability*, 13(6), p.3072.
22 632 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063072>
- 23
24 633 Burns, R. & Burns, R.P. (2008). *Business research methods and statistics using SPSS*. Sage
25 634 Publications Limited.
- 26
27 635 Carmona, I., Griffith, D. M. and Aguirre, I., (2021). Understanding the factors limiting organic
28 636 consumption: the effect of marketing channel on produce price, availability, and price fairness.
29 637 *Organic Agriculture*, 11(1), pp.89-103. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-020-00331-1>
- 30
31 638 Carolan, M., (2021). *The Sociology of Food and Agriculture*. Routledge. London.
32 639 <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003133780>
- 33
34 640 Carroll, B. E. and Fahy, F., (2015). Locating the locale of local food: The importance of context,
35 641 space and social relations. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*. Cambridge University Press,
36 642 30(6), pp.563–576. doi: 10.1017/S1742170514000404.
- 37
38 643 Chambers, S., Lobb, A., Butler, L., Harvey, K. and Traill, W.B., (2007). Local, national and imported
39 644 foods: A qualitative study. *Appetite*, 49(1), pp.208-213. DOI: 10.1016/j.appet.2007.02.003
- 40
41 645 Chiffolleau, Y. and Dourian, T., (2020). Sustainable food supply chains: Is shortening the answer? a
42 646 literature review for a research and innovation agenda. *Sustainability*, 12(23), p.9831.
43 647 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12239831>
- 44
45 648 Chiffolleau, Y., Millet-Amrani, S. and Canard, A., (2016). From short food supply chains to
46 649 sustainable agriculture in urban food systems: Food democracy as a vector of transition. *Agriculture*,
47 650 6(4),p.57. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture6040057>
- 48
49 651 Cleveland, D. A., Müller, N.M., Tranovich, A.C., Mazaroli, D.N. and Hinson, K., (2014). Local food
50 652 hubs for alternative food systems: A case study from Santa Barbara County, *California. Journal of*
51 653 *Rural Studies*, 35, pp. 26–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2014.03.008>
- 52
53 654 Conner, D., Colasanti, K., Ross, R. B. and Smalley, S. B., (2010). Locally grown foods and farmers
54 655 markets: Consumer attitudes and behaviors. *Sustainability*, 2(3), pp.742-756.
55 656 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su2030742>
- 56
57 657 Costello, A., and Osborne, J. (2005). Best practices in exploratory factor analysis: Four
58 658 recommendations for getting the most from your analysis. *Practical Assessment, Research and*
59 659 *Evaluation* 10(7), Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.umass.edu/pare/vol10/iss1/7/>. Accessed 18
60 660 September 2023.

- 661 Corvo, L., Pastore, L., Antonelli, A. and Petruzzella, D., (2021). Social Impact and Sustainability in
662 short food supply chains: an experimental assessment tool. *New Medit*, 20(3).
663 <https://doi.org/10.30682/nm21031>
- 664 Cruz, J. L., Puigdueta, I., Sanz-Cobeña, A. and González- Azcárate, M., (2021). Short Food Supply
665 Chains: rebuilding consumers' trust. *New Medit: Mediterranean Journal of Economics, Agriculture
666 and Environment=Revue Méditerranéenne d'Economie Agriculture Et Environment*, 20(4)
667 <http://dx.doi.org/10.30682/nm2104c>
- 668 Darby, K., Batte, M.T., Ernst, S. and Roe, B., (2008). Decomposing local: A conjoint analysis of
669 locally produced foods. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 90(2), pp.476-486.
- 670 De Fazio, M., (2016). Agriculture and sustainability of the welfare: the role of the short supply chain.
671 *Agriculture and agricultural science procedia*, 8, pp. 461-466.
672 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aaspro.2016.02.044>
- 673 Delicato, C., Collison, M., Myronyuk, I., Symochko, T. and Boyko, N., (2019). Is Local Better?
674 Consumer Value in Food Purchasing and the Role of Short Food Supply Chains. *Studies in
675 Agricultural Economics*, 121(1316-2019-3224), pp.75-83.
- 676 Deppermann, A., Balkovič, J., Bundle, S. C., Di Fulvio, F., Havlik, P., Leclère, D., Lesiv, M.,
677 Prishchepov, AV and Schepaschenko, D., (2018). Increasing crop production in Russia and Ukraine—
678 regional and global impacts from intensification and re-cultivation. *Environmental Research Letters*,
679 13(2), p.025008. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/aaa4a4>
- 680 Devlin, U.M., McNulty, B.A., Nugent, A.P. & Gibney, M.J. (2012). The use of cluster analysis to
681 derive dietary patterns: methodological considerations, reproducibility, validity and the effect of
682 energy mis-reporting. Pp. 599–609. Irish Section Postgraduate Symposium
- 683 Doernberg, A., Piorr, A., Zasada, I., Wascher, D. and Schmutz, U. (2022). Sustainability assessment
684 of short food supply chains (SFSC): developing and testing a rapid assessment tool in one African and
685 three European city regions. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 39, pp. 885–904.
686 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-021-10288-w>
- 687 ElHaffar, G., Durif, F., and Dubé, L. (2020). Towards closing the attitude-intention-behavior gap in
688 green consumption: A narrative review of the literature and an overview of future research directions.
689 *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 275, 1–20. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122556
- 690 Enthoven, L. and Van den Broeck, G., (2021). Local food systems: Reviewing two decades of
691 research. *Agricultural Systems*, 193, p.103226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2021.103226>
- 692 European Commission, (2013). Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the
693 Council of 17 December 2013, on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund
694 for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1698/2005. OJ L
695 (Official J. European Union L 347/487),347, pp.487-584 <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2013/1305/oj>
- 696 Farjam M., Nikolaychuk O., Bravo G. (2019). Experimental evidence of an environmental attitude-
697 behavior gap in high-cost situations. *Ecological Economics*, 166: 106434. DOI:
698 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106434
- 699 Frank, L.D., Bigazzi, A., Hong,A., Minaker, L., Fisher, P. and Raine, K.D., (2022). Built environment
700 influences on healthy eating and active living: The NEWPATH study, *Obesity*, 30(2), pp.424-434
701 <doi.org/10.1002/oby.23352>
- 702 Feldmann, C. and Hamm, U. (2015). Consumers' perceptions and preferences for local food: A
703 review. *Food Quality and Preference* 40, pp. 152–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2014.09.014>
- 704 Field, A. (2009). *Discovering statistics using SPSS*. London: Sage Publications Limited.

- 1
2
3 705 Fleury, P., Lev, L., Brives, H., Chazoule, C. and Desolé, M. (2016). Developing mid-tier supply
4 706 chains (France) and values-based food supply chains (USA): A comparison of motivations,
5 707 achievements, barriers and limitations. *Agriculture* 2016, 6(3), 36.
6 708 <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture6030036>
- 8 709 Giampietri, E., Koemle, D.B., Yu, X. and Finco, A., (2016). Consumers' sense of farmers' markets:
9 710 tasting sustainability or just purchasing food?. *Sustainability*, 8(11), p.1157.
10 711 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8111157>
- 12 712 González-Azcárate, M., Maceín, J. L. C. and Bardají, I., (2021). Why buying directly from producers
13 713 is a valuable choice? Expanding the scope of short food supply chains in Spain. *Sustainable*
14 714 *Production and Consumption*, 26, pp.911-920.
- 16 715 Goodman, D., DuPuis, E. M. and Goodman, M. K., (2012). *Alternative food networks: Knowledge,*
17 716 *practice, and politics.* Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203804520>.
- 19 717 Gruber, V. and Schlegelmilch, B.B. (2014). How Techniques of Neutralization Legitimize Norm-And
20 718 Attitude Inconsistent Consumer Behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 121 (1), pp.29–45.
21 719 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-013-1667-5>
- 23 720 Guagnano, G.A., Stern, P.C., and Dietz, T. (1995). Influences on attitude–behavior relationships: A
24 721 natural experiment with curbside recycling. *Environment and Behavior*, 27, pp. 699-718.
25 722 <https://doi.org/10.1177/00139165952750>
- 27 723 Hassan, L. M., Shiu, E., and Shaw, D. (2016). Who says there is an intentionbehavior gap?
28 724 Anssessing the empirical evidence of an intention-behavior gap in ethical consumption. *Journal of*
29 725 *Business Ethics*, 136, pp. 219–236. DOI: 10.1007/s10551-014-2440-0
- 31 726 Horlings, L. G. and Marsden, T. K., (2011). Towards the real green revolution? Exploring the
32 727 conceptual dimensions of a new ecological modernisation of agriculture that could 'feed the world'.
33 728 *Global Environmental Change*, 21(2), pp.441-452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2011.01.004>
- 35 729 Hyland, J., Olomo, Y. and Henchion, M. (2021). Report on European and regional analysis of
36 730 producer and consumers needs and barriers towards SFSCs implementation, available at
37 731 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000788/results/it>, accessed 25/9/23
- 39 732 Hyland, J. J. and Macken-Walsh, Á., (2022). Multi-Actor Social Networks: A Social Practice
40 733 Approach to Understanding Food Hubs. *Sustainability*, 14(3), p.1894.
41 734 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031894>
- 43 735 Ilbery, B. and Maye, D., (2005). Food supply chains and sustainability: evidence from specialist food
44 736 producers in the Scottish/English borders. *Land use policy*, 22(4), pp.331-344.
45 737 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2004.06.002>
- 47 738 Janssens, W., Pelsmacker, P. De, Wijnen, K. & Kenhove, P. Van. (2008). *Marketing research with*
48 739 *SPSS.* Prentice Hall.
- 50 740 Janz, N.K., and Becker, M.H. (1984). The health belief model: a decade later. *Health Education*
51 741 *Quarterly*, 11 (1), pp. 1-47. DOI: 10.1177/109019818401100101
- 53 742 Jarzębowski, S., Bourlakis, M. and Bezat-Jarzębowska, A., (2020). Short food supply chains (SFSC)
54 743 as local and sustainable systems. *Sustainability*, 12(11), p.4715. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114715>
- 56 744 Johnstone, M.L., and Tan, L.P., (2015). Exploring the gap between consumers' green rhetoric and
57 745 purchasing behaviour. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 132 (2), pp. 311–328.
58 746 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2316-3>
- 59
60

- 1
2
3 747 Kallas, Z., Alba, M. F., Casellas, K., Berges, M., Degreef, G. and Gil, J. M., (2019). The development
4 748 of short food supply chain for locally produced honey: Understanding consumers' opinions and
5 749 willingness to pay in Argentina. *British Food Journal*, 123(5), pp.1664-1680.
6 750 <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-01-2019-0070>
7
8 751 Khan, F. and Prior, C., (2010). Evaluating the urban consumer with regard to sourcing local food: a
9 752 Heart of England study. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 34(2), pp.161-168.
10 753 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1470-6431.2009.00836.x>
11
12 754 Kneafsey, M., Maye, D., Holloway, L. and Goodman, M.K., (2021). Geographies of food: an
13 755 introduction. Bloomsbury Publishing.
14
15 756 Kneafsey, M., Venn, L., Schmutz, U., Balázs, B., Trenchard, L., Eyden-Wood, T., Bos, E., Sutton, G.
16 757 and Blackett, M., (2013). Short food supply chains and local food systems in the EU. A state of play
17 758 of their socio-economic characteristics. JRC scientific and policy reports, 123, pp. 129.
18
19 759 Kovács I., Balázsné Lendvai M., and Beke J. (2022). The Importance of Food Attributes and
20 760 Motivational Factors for Purchasing Local Food Products: Segmentation of Young Local Food
21 761 Consumers in Hungary. *Sustainability*, 14, 3224. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14063224>
22
23 762 Kumar, A., and Smith, S. (2018). Understanding Local Food Consumers: Theory of Planned Behavior
24 763 and Segmentation Approach. *Journal of Food Marketing*, 24, pp. 196–215.
25 764 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10454446.2017.1266553>
26
27 765 Kumpulainen, T., Vainio, A., Sandell, M. and Hopia, A., (2018). The effect of gender, age and
28 766 product type on the origin induced food product experience among young consumers in Finland.
29 767 *Appetite*, 123, pp.101-107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2017.12.011>
30
31 768 Kwant, J., (2021). Consumer Attitudes on the Intention to Purchase Local Food Products in Sweden,
32 769 Belgium, Germany, Denmark, and the Netherlands. Consumer Attitudes on the Intention to Purchase
33 770 Local Food Products in Sweden, Belgium, Germany, Denmark, and the Netherlands.
34
35 771 Kwasnicka, D., Dombrowski, S.U., White, M., and Sniehotta, F. (2016). Theoretical explanations for
36 772 maintenance of behaviour change: A systematic review of behaviour theories. *Health Psychology*
37 773 *Review*, pp. 277–296. DOI: 10.1080/17437199.2016.1151372
38
39 774 Longin, C. F. H. and Würschum, T., (2016). Back to the future—tapping into ancient grains for food
40 775 diversity. *Trends in Plant Science*, 21(9), pp.731-737. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2016.05.005>
41
42 776 Labrecque, J. S., Wood, W., Neal, D. T., and Harrington, N. (2017). Habit slips: When consumers
43 777 unintentionally resist new products. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, (45), pp. 119-133.
44 778 DOI: 10.1007/s11747-016-0482-9
45
46 779 Leeuwis N., van Bommel, T. and Alimardani, M. (2022). A framework for application of consumer
47 780 neuroscience in pro-environmental behaviour change interventions. *Frontiers in Human*
48 781 *Neuroscience*, 16:886600. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2022.886600>
49
50 782 Li, Y., Lu, Y., Zhang, X., Liu, L., Wang, M., Jiang, X. (2016). Propensity of green consumption
51 783 behaviors in representative cities in China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 133, pp. 1328–1336. DOI:
52 784 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.012
53
54 785 Lim, K.H., Hu, W., Maynard, L.J. and Goddard, E., (2013). US consumers' preference and
55 786 willingness to pay for country-of-origin-labeled beef steak and food safety enhancements. *Canadian*
56 787 *Journal of Agricultural Economics/Revue canadienne d'agroeconomie*, 61(1), pp.93-118.
57 788 10.22004/ag.econ.103385
58
59 789 Lynes, J., (2015). Identification of barriers and benefits for Jack Johnson's 'All at Once' Campaign. In
60 790 World Social marketing conference.

- 1
2
3 791 MacDonald, P.L. & Gardner, R.C. (2000). Type I Error Rate Comparisons of Post Hoc Procedures for
4 792 I j Chi-Square Tables. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 60, 735–754.
5 793 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164002197087>
6
7 794 Magistris, T.D and Gracia, A., (2014). Do consumers care about organic and distance labels? An
8 795 empirical analysis in S pain. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 38(6), pp.660-669.
9 796 <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12138>
10
11 797 Mancini, M., Menozzi, D., Donati, M., Biasini, B., Veneziani, M. and Arfini, F., (2019). Producers'
12 798 and Consumers' Perception of the Sustainability of Short Food Supply Chains: The Case of
13 799 Parmigiano Reggiano PDO. *Sustainability*, 11(3), p.721. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11030721>
14
15 800 Marsden, T., Banks, J. and Bristow, G., (2000). Food supply chain approaches: exploring their role in
16 801 rural development. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 40(4), pp.424-438. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9523.00158>
17
18 802 Maxey, L. (2007). From “alternative” to “sustainable” food. In D. Maye, L. Holloway, & M.
19 803 Kneafsey(Eds.), *Alternative Food Geographies*. London: Elsevier.
20
21 804 Mbow, C., Rosenzweig, C., Barioni, L.G., Benton, T.G., Shukla, P.R., Skea, J., Calvo Buendia, E.,
22 805 Masson Delmotte, V., Pörtner, H.-O., Roberts, D.C., et al. (2019). Climate Change and Land. Chapter
23 806 5: Food Security. In IPCC SPECIAL REPORT Global Warming of 1.5 oC; IPCC, Ed.; 2019; pp. 1–
24 807 200.
25
26 808 Megicks, P., Memery, J. and Angell, R.J., (2012). Understanding local food shopping: Unpacking the
27 809 ethical dimension. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 28(3-4), pp.264-289. DOI:
28 810 10.1080/0267257X.2012.658838
29
30 811 Mesić, Ž., Petljak, K., Borović, D. and Tomić, M., (2020). Segmentation of local food consumers
31 812 based on altruistic motives and perceived purchasing barriers: a Croatian study. *Economic Research-*
32 813 *Ekonomiska Istraživanja*, 34(1), pp.221-242. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2020.1782243>
33
34 814 Meynard, J. M., Jeuffroy, M. H., Le Bail, M., Lefèvre, A., Magrini, M. B. and Michon, C., (2017).
35 815 Designing coupled innovations for the sustainability transition of agrifood systems. *Agricultural*
36 816 *Systems*, 157, pp.330-339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2016.08.002>
37
38 817 Michaelsen, M. M., & Esch, T. (2021). Motivation and reward mechanisms in health behavior change
39 818 processes. *Brain Research*, 1757, 147309. DOI: 10.1016/j.brainres.2021.147309
40
41 819 Michel-Villarreal, R., Vilalta-Perdomo, E. L., Canavari, M. and Hingley, M., (2021). Resilience and
42 820 Digitalization in Short Food Supply Chains: A Case Study Approach. *Sustainability*, 13(11), p.5913.
43 821 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13115913>
44
45 822 Miroso, M. and Lawson, R., (2012). Revealing the lifestyles of local food consumers. *British Food*
46 823 *Journal*, 114(6), pp.816-825. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00070701211234345>
47
48 824 Morris, C. and Buller, H., (2003). The local food sector: a preliminary assessment of its form and
49 825 impact in Gloucestershire. *British Food Journal*, 105(8), pp.559-566. DOI:
50 826 10.1108/00070700310497318
51
52 827 Mundler, P. and Laughrea, S., (2016). The contributions of short food supply chains to territorial
53 828 development: A study of three Quebec territories. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 45, pp.218-229.
54 829 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2016.04.001>
55
56 830 Nguyen, H. V., Nguyen, C. H., & Hoang, T. T. B. (2019). Green consumption: Closing the intention-
57 831 behaviour gap. *Sustainable Development*, 27(1), pp. 118–129. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.1875>
58
59 832 Nie, C. and Zepeda, L. (2011). Lifestyle Segmentation of US Food Shoppers to Examine Organic and
60 833 Local Food Consumption. *Appetite*, 57 (1): pp. 28–37. DOI: 10.1016/j.appet.2011.03.012

- 1
2
3 834 Nowak, A., Vallacher, R.R., Tesser, A., Borkowski, W. (2000). Society of self: the emergence of
4 835 collective properties in self-structure. *Psychological Review*, 107 (1), pp. 39.
5 836 <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.107.1.39>
6
7 837 Nunnally, J. (1967). *Psychometric theory*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
8
9 838 Nurse, G., Onozaka, Y. and Hilmany, D., (2012). Consumer motivations and buying behavior: The
10 839 case of the local food system movement. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 18(5), pp.385-396.
11 840 DOI: 10.1080/10454446.2012.685031
12
13 841 Padel, S., & Foster, C. (2005). Understanding why consumers buy or do not buy organic food. *British*
14 842 *Food Journal*, 107(8), pp. 606–625. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00070700510611002>
15
16 843 Pallant, J. (2010). *SPSS survival manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using SPSS*. London:
17 844 Open University Press.
18
19 845 Pearson, D., Henryks, J. and Jones, H., (2011). Organic food: What we know (and do not know) about
20 846 consumers. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*, 26(2), pp.171-177. DOI:
21 847 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742170510000499>
22
23 848 Peattie, K. (2010). Green consumption: Behavior and norms. *Annual Review of Environment and*
24 849 *Resources*, 35(1), pp. 195–228. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-032609-094328>
25
26 850 Penney, U. and Prior, C., (2014). Exploring the urban consumer's perception of local food.
27 851 *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 42(7), pp.580-594.
28 852 <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-09-2012-0077>
29
30 853 Ribeiro, A., Harmsen, R., Feola, G., Rosales Carréon, J. and Worrell, E., (2021). Organising
31 854 alternative food networks (AFNs): Challenges and facilitating conditions of different AFN types in
32 855 three EU countries. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 61(2), pp.491-517. <https://doi.org/10.1111/soru.12331>
33
34 856 Rasul, G., (2021). Twin challenges of COVID-19 pandemic and climate change for agriculture and
35 857 food security in South Asia. *Environmental Challenges*, 2, p.100027.
36 858 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2021.100027>
37
38 859 Reedy, J., Wirfält, E., Flood, A., Mitrou, P.N., Krebs-Smith, S.M., Kipnis, V., Midthune, D.,
39 860 Leitzmann, M., Hollenbeck, A., Schatzkin, A. & Subar, A.F. (2010). Comparing 3 dietary pattern
40 861 methods--cluster analysis, factor analysis, and index analysis--With colorectal cancer risk: The NIH-
41 862 AARP Diet and Health Study. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 171, 479–87. doi:
42 863 10.1093/aje/kwp393.
43
44 864 Rey-Moreno, M., & Medina-Molina, C. (2020). Dual models and technological platforms for efficient
45 865 management of water consumption. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 150. Article
46 866 119761. DOI: 10.1016/j.techfore.2019.119761
47
48 867 Ribeiro, A.P., Rok, J., Harmsen, R., Carreón, J.R. and Worrell, E., (2019). Food waste in an
49 868 alternative food network—A case-study. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 149, pp.210-219.
50 869 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.05.029>
51
52 870 Richetin, J., and Perugini, M. (2022). The organic diet effect on person perception. *Appetite*, 168,
53 871 105696. DOI: 10.1016/j.appet.2021.105696
54
55 872 Robinson-O'Brien, R., Larson, N., Neumark-Sztainer, D., Hannan, P. and Story, M., (2009).
56 873 Characteristics and dietary patterns of adolescents who value eating locally grown, organic,
57 874 nongenetically engineered, and nonprocessed food. *Journal of Nutrition Education and Behavior*,
58 875 41(1), pp.11-18. DOI: 10.1016/j.jneb.2008.03.007
59
60

- 1
2
3 876 Roy, H., Hall, C. M. and Ballantine, P. W., (2017). Trust in local food networks: The role of trust
4 877 among tourism stakeholders and their impacts in purchasing decisions. *Journal of Destination*
5 878 *Marketing & Management*, 6(4), pp.309-317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2017.07.002>
- 7 879 Sacchi, G., Cei, L., Stefani, G., Lombardi, G.V., Rocchi, B., Belletti, G., Padel, S., Sellars, A.,
8 880 Gagliardi, E., Nocella, G. and Cardey, S., (2018). A multi-actor literature review on alternative and
9 881 sustainable food systems for the promotion of cereal biodiversity. *Agriculture*, 8(11), p.173.
10 882 <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture8110173>
- 12 883 Sahu, A.K., Padhy, R. K., and Dhir. A. (2020). Envisioning the Future of Behavioral Decision-
13 884 Making: A Systematic Literature Review of Behavioral Reasoning Theory. *Australasian Marketing*
14 885 *Journal*, 28(4), pp. 145-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ausmj.2020.05.001>
- 16 886 Sebök, A., Varsányi, K., Parrag, V., Braun, S., Fricz, Á. S. and Casado, J., (2020). Elimination of
17 887 Bottlenecks of Short Food Chains by Technological and Non-technological Innovations in Short Food
18 888 Supply Chains. *Proceedings in Food System Dynamics*, pp.42-62.
- 20 889 Sharpe, D. (2019). Chi-Square Test Is Statistically Significant: Now What? - Practical Assessment,
21 890 *Research and Evaluation*, 20, 2-10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7275/tbfa-x148>
- 23 891 Shin, Y. H. and Hancer, M., (2016). The role of attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral
24 892 control, and moral norm in the intention to purchase local food products. *Journal of Foodservice*
25 893 *Business research*, 19(4), pp.338-351. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15378020.2016.1181506>
- 27 894 Sirieix, L., Delanchy, M., Remaud, H., Zepeda L., and Gurviez, P. (2013). Consumers' perceptions of
28 895 individual and combined sustainable food labels: A UK pilot investigation. *International Journal of*
29 896 *Consumer Studies*, 37, pp. 143-151. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1470-6431.2012.01109.x>
- 31 897 Sirieix, L., Grolleau, G. and Schaer, B., (2008). Do consumers care about food miles? An empirical
32 898 analysis in France. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 32(5), pp.508-515.
33 899 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1470-6431.2008.00711.x>
- 35 900 Snyder, M. (1992). Motivational foundations of behavioral confirmation *Advances in Experimental*
36 901 *Social Psychology*, 25, pp. 67-114. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(08\)60282-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(08)60282-8)
- 38 902 Stein, A. J. and Santini, F., (2021). The sustainability of "local" food: a review for policy-makers.
39 903 *Review of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Studies*, pp.1-13. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s41130-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s41130-021-00148-w)
40 904 [021-00148-w](https://doi.org/10.1007/s41130-021-00148-w)
- 42 905 Stern, P.C. (2000). Toward a coherent theory of environmentally significant behaviour. *Journal of*
43 906 *Social Issues*, 56 (2000), pp. 407-424. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0022-4537.00175>
- 45 907 Tandon, A., Jabeen, F., Talwar, S., Sakashita, M., and Dhir, A. (2021). Facilitators and inhibitors of
46 908 organic food buying behavior. *Food Quality and Preference*, 88, 104077.
47 909 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2020.104077>
- 49 910 Thaler, R.H. (1999). Mental accounting matters. *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making*, 12 (3), pp.
50 911 183-206.
- 52 912 Therond, O., Duru, M., Roger-Estrade, J. and Richard, G., (2017). A new analytical framework of
53 913 farming system and agriculture model diversities. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*,
54 914 37(3), pp.1-24.
- 56 915 Thomas, J.B., Clark, S.M. and Gioia, D.A., (1993). Strategic sensemaking and organizational
57 916 performance: Linkages among scanning, interpretation, action, and outcomes. *Academy of*
58 917 *Management journal*, 36(2), pp.239-270. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256522>
- 59
60

- 1
2
3 918 Tippins, M.J., Rassuli, K.M. and Hollander, S.C., (2002). An assessment of direct farm-to-table food
4 919 marketing in the USA. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 30(7), pp.343-
5 920 353.
- 7 921 Trobe, H. L. (2001). Farmers' markets: Consuming local rural produce farmers' markets: Local rural
8 922 produce. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 25(3), pp. 181–192. DOI: 10.1046/j.1470-
9 923 6431.2001.00171.x
- 11 924 Tundys, B. and Wiśniewski, T., (2020). Benefit optimization of short food supply chains for organic
12 925 products: A simulation-based approach. *Applied Sciences*, 10(8), p.2783.
13 926 <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10082783>
- 15 927 van de Grint, L. T. M., Evans, A. M., and Stavrova, O. (2021). Good eats, bad intentions?
16 928 Reputational costs of organic consumption. *Journal of Environmental Psychology* (75), 101622.
17 929 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2021.101622>
- 19 930 Vermeir, I. and Verbeke, W., (2008). Sustainable food consumption among young adults in Belgium:
20 931 Theory of planned behaviour and the role of confidence and values. *Ecological Economics*, 64(3),
21 932 pp.542-553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2007.03.007>
- 23 933 Vermeir, I. and Verbeke, W., (2006). Sustainable food consumption: Exploring the consumer
24 934 “attitude–behavioral intention” gap. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*, 19, pp.169-
25 935 194. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10806-005-5485-3>
- 27 936 Verplanken, B., and Orbell, S. (2022). Attitudes, habits and behavior change. *Annual Review of*
28 937 *Psychology*, 73, pp. 327–352. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-020821-011744>
- 30 938 Vieira, J., Castro, S.L., Souza, A.S. (2023). Psychological barriers moderate the attitude-behavior gap
31 939 for climate change. *PLoS ONE*, 18, e0287404. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0287404>
- 33 940 Vogt, L. and Mergenthaler, M., (2015). A typification of short food supply chains and first insights
34 941 into respective success factors and bottlenecks in North Rhine-Westphalia. *Economic developments*
35 942 *in rural areas: Functional and multifunctional approaches*, pp.83-108.
- 37 943 Wang, M., Kumar, V., Ruan, X., Saad, M., Garza-Reyes, J. A. and Kumar, A., (2021). Sustainability
38 944 concerns on consumers' attitude towards short food supply chains: an empirical investigation.
39 945 *Operations Management Research*, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12063-021-00188-x>
- 41 946 Watts, D. C., Ilbery, B. and Maye, D., (2017). Making reconstructions in agro-food geography:
42 947 alternative systems of food provision. *The Rural*, pp.165-184.
43 948 <https://doi.org/10.1191/0309132505ph526oa>
- 45 949 Wiederhold, M., & Martinez, L. F. (2018). Ethical consumer behaviour in Germany: The
46 950 attitude-behaviour gap in the green apparel industry. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*,
47 951 42(4), pp. 419-429. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12435>
- 49 952 Witzling, L., and Shaw, B.R. (2019). Lifestyle Segmentation and Political Ideology: Toward
50 953 Understanding Beliefs and Behavior about Local Food. *Appetite*, 132, pp. 106–113.
51 954 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2018.10.003>
- 53 955 Young, W., Hwang, K., McDonald, S., & Oates, C.J. (2010). Sustainable consumption: Green
54 956 consumer behaviour when purchasing products. *Sustainable Development*, 18(1), 20–31. DOI:
55 957 10.1002/sd.394
- 57 958 Zapico, L.J., Katzeff, C., Bohné, U., and Milestad, R. (2016). Eco-Feedback Visualization for Closing
58 959 the Gap of Organic Food Consumption. In *Proceedings of the 9th Nordic Conference on Human-*
59 960 *Computer Interaction (Gothenburg, Sweden) (NordCHI '16)*. Association for Computing Machinery,
60 961 New York, NY, USA, Article 75, 9 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2971485.2971507>

- 1
2
3 962 Zepeda, L. and Deal, D., (2009). Organic and local food consumer behaviour: Alphabet theory.
4 963 *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 33(6), pp.697-705. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1470->
5 964 6431.2009.00814.x
- 7 965 Zepeda, L. and Leviten-Reid, C., (2004). Consumers' views on local food. *Journal of food distribution*
8 966 *Research*, 35(856-2016-56647), pp.1-6.
- 10 967 Zimon, D., Tyan, J. and Sroufe, R., (2020). Drivers of sustainable supply chain management:
11 968 Practices to alignment with un sustainable development goals. *International Journal for Quality*
12 969 *Research*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.24874/IJQR14.01-14>
- 13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

British Food Journal

Table 1: The main barriers consumers face when purchasing food from SFSCS¹

Barriers in purchasing food from SFSCs	References
Inconvenience and lack of availability	Trobe, 2001; Zepeda and Leviten-Reid, 2004; Stephenson and Lev, 2004; Sirieix, Grolleau and Schaer, 2008; Conner <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Khan and Prior, 2010; Bean and Sharp, 2011; Pearson <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Megicks, Memery and Angell, 2012; Penney and Prior, 2014; Mesić <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
High price of local food	Zepeda and Leviten-Reid, 2004; Chambers <i>et al.</i> , 2007; Sirieix, Grolleau and Schaer, 2008; Khan and Prior, 2010; Penney and Prior, 2014; Lynes, 2015; Mesić <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Lack of time / time pressure faced by consumers	(Tippins, Rassuli and Hollander, 2002; Chambers <i>et al.</i> , 2007; Sirieix, Grolleau and Schaer, 2008; Conner <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Khan and Prior, 2010)
Lack of trust in the authenticity of local food/food from a SFSC	(Bingen, Sage and Sirieix, 2011; Birch and Memery, 2020; Mesić <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Limited promotion	(Pearson <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Penney and Prior, 2014; Kwant, 2021)
Lack of knowledge	(Brown, 2003; Robinson-O'Brien <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Zepeda and Deal, 2009; Miroso and Lawson, 2012; Sirieix <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Feldmann and Hamm, 2015; Sebök <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Kwant, 2021)
Lack of motivation	(Vermeir and Verbeke, 2006, 2008; Darby <i>et al.</i> , 2008; Zepeda and Deal, 2009; Conner <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Lim <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Feldmann and Hamm, 2015; Shin and Hancer, 2016; Birch, Memery and Kanakarantne, 2018; Mesić <i>et al.</i> , 2021)

¹ Table adapted from Mesić et al. (2021)

Table 2. Component loadings derived from PCA of questionnaire statements (after Varimax rotation)

	Component		
	1	2	3
Support local famers and food producers	.839	-.120	.000
Support of the local economy	.822	-.123	.039
Appreciation of craft or artisan methods	.794	-.134	.049
Being able to trust SFSC producers	.780	-.178	.000
Environmental attributes of products	.762	-.250	.064
Learning about where food has come from	.759	-.255	.078
Preservation of local traditions and heritage	.753	-.186	.098
Lower transport miles	.710	-.197	.024
Interaction with food producers	.702	-.244	.140
Quality attributes (taste, freshness, healthiness)	.685	-.190	-.041
Food safety concerns	.600	-.257	.048
Impact of Covid-19 pandemic	.479	-.379	.189
Inconvenience of buying SFSC food	-.128	.750	-.047
There is a limited range of products	-.067	.731	-.026
Products not available throughout the year	-.129	.727	-.108
Unreliability of delivery service	-.154	.727	-.099
SFSC producers do not effectively communicate benefits	-.286	.724	-.074
Variability of product quality	-.214	.719	-.082
Lack of trust	-.270	.681	-.110
Products are more expensive than conventional products	-.025	.679	.132
Lack of awareness of the benefits	-.298	.669	-.103
Inability to differentiate SFSC products from conventional products	-.268	.667	-.032
Lack of options for online ordering	-.182	.665	-.077
Covid-19 has made it more difficult	-.246	.661	-.145
Lack of local outlets (market stalls/shops/restaurants etc.)	-.393	.584	.063
Dairy SFSC purchase frequency	.073	-.031	.838
Meat SFSC purchase frequency	.026	-.056	.818
Other SFSC purchase frequency	-.053	-.160	.777
Eggs SFSC purchase frequency	.157	-.006	.773
Baked goods SFSC purchase frequency	.136	.015	.768
Fish SFSC purchase frequency	.062	-.043	.762
Non-perishables SFSC purchase frequency	-.035	-.130	.758
Fruit and vegetables SFSC purchase frequency	.206	.022	.742
Ready meals SFSC purchase frequency	-.115	-.138	.673

Component scores denoted in bold represent factor scores allocated to that specific component

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Table 3 Final cluster centres

	Clusters			
	Unaware Unengaged (22.0%)	Aware Unengaged (27.8%)	Motivationally Engaged (18.8%)	Executively Engaged (31.4%)
Motivation score	-1.18	-0.112	0.85	0.42
Barrier score	-0.29	0.26	-1.25	0.72
Purchase frequency score	0.58	-1.20	0.04	0.64

British Food Journal

Table 4 Demographic profile of each cluster (%)

		Unaware Unengaged	Aware Unengaged	Motivationally Engaged	Executively Engaged
Region	Eastern Europe	37.6 _a	20.7 _b	14.8 _b	27.4 _c
	Mediterranean	21.6 _a	30.8 _b	28.0 _{ab}	46.6 _c
	Nordic	18.2 _a	21.8 _a	21.4 _a	8.0 _b
	Western Europe	22.6 _{ab}	26.7 _b	35.9 _c	18.0 _a
Location	Rural	15.0 _a	17.50 _a	25.60 _b	14.90 _a
	Suburban	32.0 _a	31.8 _a	33.7 _a	28.5 _a
	Urban	53.0 _a	50.7 _a	40.7 _b	56.7 _a
Age group	18-24	13.5 _a	10.7 _{ab}	6.2 _b	9.0 _{ab}
	25-39	28.6 _a	23.1 _a	19.4 _a	24.4 _a
	40-54	25.9 _a	28.6 _a	23.1 _a	26.6 _a
	55-64	14.7 _a	15.9 _a	24.2 _b	16.6 _a
	≥ 65	17.3 _a	21.7 _{ab}	27.1 _b	23.5 _b
Household income/year	< €25,000	41.5 _a	42.2 _a	30.9 _b	39.3 _a
	€25,001 - €35,000	15.5 _a	19.1 _a	20.5 _a	18.9 _a
	€35,001 - €50,000	19.5 _a	17.4 _a	22.5 _a	14.8 _a
	€50,001 - €75,000	9.7 _a	11.5 _a	12.8 _a	13.5 _a
	€75,001 - €100,00	6.6 _a	6.1 _a	7.9 _a	4.8 _a
	€100,001 - €150,000	3.6 _a	3.2 _a	2.7 _a	3.3 _a
	€150,001 - €200,000	1.7 _a	0.3 _a	1.7 _a	2.1 _a
≥ €200,001	1.9 _{ab}	0.3 _b	1.0 _{ab}	3.3 _a	
Education	No formal	1.3 _a	1.8 _a	1.5 _a	1.1 _a
	Primary	4.0 _a	4.3 _a	4.6 _a	3.2 _a
	Secondary	31.7 _a	24.2 _a	25.8 _a	25.8 _a
	Post-secondary	17.8 _a	19.3 _a	21.2 _a	18.6 _a
	Undergraduate degree	29.3 _a	31.4 _a	25.8 _a	30.6 _a
	Postgraduate degree	15.9 _a	19 _a	21.0 _a	20.7 _a
Employment type	Farmer	1.1 _a	0.4 _a	1.3 _a	1.7 _a
	Self-employed	7.1 _a	8.8 _a	5.5 _a	6.3 _a
	Manager	6.8 _{ab}	5.2 _b	6.8 _{ab}	10.0 _a
	Other white collar	22.7 _a	21.1 _a	21.6 _a	20.6 _a
	Blue collar	15.4 _a	14.0 _a	14.1 _a	13.4 _a
	House person	5.6 _a	4.3 _a	4.4 _a	6.7 _a
	Unemployed	6.6 _a	6.4 _a	3.5 _a	5.0 _a
	Retired	20.3 _a	22.8 _a	31.9 _b	23.6 _a
	Student	8.1 _a	7.6 _a	4.2 _a	5.0 _a
	Other	6.4 _a	9.4 _a	6.6 _a	7.6 _a

Superscript letters indicates significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between clusters after Chi-Square test with Bonferroni correction

Table 5 Purchasing behaviour of clusters in regard to number of household shoppers and the proportional value of SFSC products purchased in a month (%)

		Unaware Unengaged	Aware Unengaged	Motivationally Engaged	Executively Engaged
No. of household grocery shoppers	1	21.2 _a	25.6 _a	23.2 _a	13.4 _b
	2	33.6 _a	39.2 _a	40.8 _a	32.1 _a
	3	20.1 _a	17.2 _a	16.1 _a	21.4 _a
	4	15.8 _{ab}	9.7 _c	13.5 _{ac}	20.4 _b
	5	6.9 _a	5.1 _a	5.1 _a	7.6 _a
	≥ 6	2.4 _{ab}	3.3 _{ab}	1.3 _a	5.0 _b
Value of SFSC food purchased/month	0%				
	1-25%	13.3 _a	27.9 _b	2.4 _c	5.5 _c
	26-50%	53.2 _a	65.1 _b	54.0 _a	35.9 _c
	51-75%	28.4 _a	6.1 _b	31.9 _a	40.1 _c
	76- 100%	4.7 _a	0.7 _b	10.1 _c	15.5 _d
	100%	0.4 _{ab}	0.1 _b	1.5 _{ac}	2.9 _c

Superscript letters indicates significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between clusters after Chi-Square test with Bonferroni correction

Supplementary Table 1: Sample profile (n=2,419)

Sample Characteristics		
Age	Frequency	Percent (%)
18 -24	239	9.9
25 -39	582	24.1
40 -54	637	26.4
55 - 64	421	17.4
65 and above	539	22.3
Total	2419	100.0
Geographic location: Type of Area	Frequency	Percent (%)
Rural (thinly populated areas)	429	17.7
Suburban (populated areas of intermediate density)	753	48.8
Urban (densely populated areas)	1237	51.2
Total	2419	100.0
Education: Level of education	Frequency	Percent (%)
No formal education	34	1.4
Primary	97	4.0
Secondary	640	26.4
Post-secondary (non-tertiary)	459	19.0
Undergraduate tertiary degree (i.e. Bachelor's degree)	712	29.4
Postgraduate degree (i.e. Masters, PhD)	462	19.1
Prefer not to say	16	0.7
Total	2419	100.0
Annual household income (before tax)	Frequency	Percent (%)
Less than €25,000	848	35.0
€25,001 - €35,000	401	16.6
€35,001 - €50,000	390	16.1
€50,001 - €75,000	261	10.8
€75,001 - €100,000	133	5.5
€100,001 - €150,000	70	2.9
€150,001 - €200,000	32	1.3
€200,001 and above	38	1.6
Prefer not to say	246	10.2
Total	2419	100.0
Employment : Job category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Farmer/Fisher/Grower/ Primary Food Producer	28	1.2
Self-employed (not including Farmer/Fisher/Grower/Primary Producer)	170	7.0
Manager	179	7.4
Other white collar	517	21.4
Blue collar (manual worker)	342	14.1
House person (a person who manages a household)	130	5.4
Unemployed	133	5.5
Retired	584	24.2
Student	150	6.2
Other	186	7.7
Total	2419	100.0

Supplementary Table 2: Good Practices and the consumer barriers they mitigate

Consumer Barriers towards the purchase of SFSC products	Potential Mitigation	Good Practice
1. Lack of local outlets (market talls/shops/restaurants etc.) that sell SFSC products	Online ordering, mobile farmers market	Neighbourfoods, Pora Na Pola, Rechtstreeex, Mobilus Turgelis
2. Products are more expensive than conventional products	Membership fees that share risk to avoid excessive costing, self-picking, or contributing work, subscriptions that are lower in price but ensure regular customers	Bios coop, Self-picking of berries, Telaraki, Københavns Fødevarefællessk
3. Variability of product quality	Improve the quality and safety of traditional foods	TRUEFOOD
4. Lack of trust where the product comes from	Community supported agriculture and direct purchasing	Cloughjordan eco-farm, REKO Food collective
5. Inability to differentiate SFSC products from conventional products	Small local retailers with extensive product knowledge, online meeting point to identify SFSC producers, retailers and food service businesses	The Little Cheese Shop Dingle, GASTROTECA
6. SFSC producers do not effectively communicate the benefits of the model	Awareness raising	LA OSA COOP, La Ruche qui dit Oui
7. Unreliability of delivery service	Weekly pick-up location	REKO Food collective
8. Lack of awareness of the benefits concerning SFSCs	Education	Airfield Estate
9. There is a limited range of products	Farmers markets	Cassetta Rossa
10. Products not available throughout the year	Education	Airfield Estate, kindergarten
11. Inconvenience of buying SFSC food	Farmers markets	Cassetta Rossa
12. Lack of options for online ordering	One online location that brings SFSC products to one place	Neighbourfoods, Pora Na Pola
13. Covid-19 has made it more difficult to purchase though SFSCs	Online ordering and delivery	Neighbourfoods, Pora Na Pola

Source: <https://www.agrobridges.eu/interactive-catalogue-agrobridges>